

The Assessment of Users' Preference for Print or e-resource in Centrally Funded Institutions of Jabalpur Madhya Pradesh: A study

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Abstract: The library is a vital institution that stores and disseminates reading materials for teaching, research, and entertainment. It contains print and electronic resources, providing access to information through e-books, online journals, databases, and multimedia content. This study investigates users' preferences for study materials such as print or in digital form or both combinations in centrally funded Jabalpur Madhya Pradesh institutions and whether they download or access electronic resources online. The research aims to identify the factors influencing users' choice between print, e-resources, and hybrid mode. The study employs a mixed-method approach, combining quantitative and qualitative data collection and analysis methods. The study's findings will provide insights into user behavior, preferences, and expectations, which can inform library collection development, resource allocation, and service delivery strategies in centrally funded institutions. The study outcomes also contribute to the existing knowledge on user preference for print and E-resources and will have implications for the region's libraries, policymakers, and educators.

Keywords: Print Resources, E-Resources, User preference, centrally funded institutions, Jabalpur Madhya Pradesh

Introduction: The library is a vital part of any institution where reading material related to teaching, research, and entertainment is stored and disseminated. Print and electronic resources are two crucial parts of the library collection that provide different ways to access and interact with information. E-books, online journals, databases, multimedia content, and web-based resources are all considered electronic resources. Users can quickly and easily find information with the help of quick access, search capability, and remote availability features of these resources. However, books, magazines, newspapers, and other tangible materials that provide a tactile and concrete reading experience are examples of print resources. Printed materials often offer historical context, in-depth scholarly analysis, and the tactile pleasure of reading actual books. Libraries must balance the strengths of both print and electronic resources to meet their patrons' various needs and preferences.

Central government funded in Jabalpur, Madhya Pradesh, plays a significant role in education, research, and development. Notable institutions include IIITDM Jabalpur, which specializes in engineering, design, and manufacturing and promotes innovation and interdisciplinary research. At the same time, NIRTH Jabalpur focuses on tribal health research, addressing diseases, and improving healthcare in tribal communities. DWR Jabalpur researches sustainable weed management to support agriculture and environmental preservation. These institutions contribute to the region's academic excellence, public health, and agricultural advancement.

Institution Introduction: Madhya Pradesh's historic city of Jabalpur is renowned for its natural beauty, cultural diversity, and growing importance as a center of education. The town has several centrally funded institutions contributing to research, development, and education.

1. **IIITDM Jabalpur:** To foster excellence in IT, design, manufacturing, and competitive advantage in international markets. The Indian Institute of information technology design and manufacturing Jabalpur was founded in 2005. To integrate knowledge from multiple disciplines with IT-enabled design, prototyping, and manufacturing considerations. The institute focuses on fast concept, venture capital, and product lifecycle management. The institution's library has a rich print and non-print study material collection. The library provides access to numerous e-resources, including online journals from reputed publishers like IEEE, Springer, Elsevier, and ACM—databases like Scopus, JSTOR, and Science Direct.

2. **DWR Jabalpur:** To tack the weed flora and economic viability in 11 Indian states, The ICAR launched the coordinated Weed Control Scheme in 1952. The Weed Research Program was reinforced in 1978 by establishing six centers at state agriculture universities. 1989 The National Research Centre for Weed Science was founded to manage weeds. Specialized weed science materials such as technical reports, manuals on weed management techniques, and monographs are kept in the DWR library. Availability of databases for agricultural research, including CAB abstracts and AGRICOLA, online access to agricultural and environmental science journals and conference proceedings

3. NIRTH Jabalpur: The ICMR-National Institute of Research in Tribal Health, established in 1984, researches health issues in tribal populations, including nutritional disorders and diseases. It offers health professional training and supports state health departments with diagnosis, planning, monitoring, and evaluation. In Himachal Pradesh, the institute also maintains a field unit. A subscription to major medical databases like PubMed, MEDLINE, and Cochrane Library access to international health research journals and articles, a vast collection of medical literature including books, journals, reports, guidelines about public health, tribal health, and communicable diseases, and accessibility to a verity of digital resources

Review of Literature:

1. K, Haneefa Mohamed (2020), Students' Preference of Reading Print and Digital Resources: A Study in Universities in Kerala, India, A study comparing print and digital reading media among postgraduate students from four Kerala state universities found that students prefer print for reading books, magazines, and dissertations. Digital materials offer flexibility, remote access, and up-to-date information, while print is selected for note-taking, leisure reading, and in-depth reading. Teachers and publishers must collaborate to help students become better readers.

2. Idiegbeyan-ose, Jerome & Ifijeh, Goodluck (2019), E-Resources vs Prints Usages and Preferences by Undergraduates in a Private University Nigeria, The study examines Nigerian undergraduates' usage and preferences of e-resources at a private university. With 92.45% of respondents answering a questionnaire, it emphasizes the importance of print and electronic resources in education and encourages library preservation.

3. Bhat, Nazir Ahmad & Ganaie, Shabir Ahmad (2018), Assessment of user preference to information resources in agricultural libraries in North India, The study examines user preferences for electronic information resources (EIRs) and access methods of farm libraries in North India. A survey with 1275 completed questionnaires revealed 85% response rate. The study suggests equal distribution of resources and changes in the digital information landscape.

4. Gupta, Sujata (2016), Preference and Use of Print and E-Resources among Faculties and Students: A Study of Vasantha College for Women, The study examines library patrons' preferences for print and electronic resources. Despite concerns about preservation, research requirements, content quality, document control, and authenticity, students, faculty, postgraduates, and undergraduates still prefer print materials over e-resources, highlighting the need for updated library services.

5. Cherian, Jacob & Jacob, Jolly (2013), Analysis of Attitude towards Online and Print Publications: A Case, The study reveals that young adults in India prefer print editions for advertising revenue, but the future of print media is uncertain due to issues with payment methods, copyright enforcement, encryption, and metering technology. The study suggests newspapers should adapt their tactics to accommodate this disinterest in news.

Objective of the study: The primary purpose of the study is to understand

1. Users prefer print or E-resources in the centrally funded Jabalpur Madhya Pradesh institutions.
2. Users prefer downloading the information or only reading the information in centrally funded institutions of Jabalpur Madhya Pradesh.

Research Methodology

Research Design: The present study employs a descriptive survey research design to access users' preferences for print and e-resources in centrally funded institutions of Jabalpur, Madhya Pradesh. The study evaluates users' choices, factors influencing their preferences, and satisfaction levels with print and electronic resources. A mixed-methods approach, incorporating qualitative and quantitative data, was employed to understand user preference and gather data.

Population and Sampling: The targeted population consists of students, faculty members, and researchers from centrally funded institutions in Jabalpur, Such as IIITDM, NIRTH, and DWR

Data Collection Method: A well-structured questionnaire was given to Students, Faculty, and researchers at Jabalpur's centrally funded institutions. In-depth interviews were also carried out to obtain qualitative insights. We have taken three central-funded institutions in Jabalpur, Madhya Pradesh, in our sample.

Method of Analysis: Statistical tools were used for data analysis to find trends and correlations.

Findings:

Table 1

Users' preference for print or E-resources in centrally funded institutions of Jabalpur Madhya Pradesh					
S. No.	Name of Institutions	E-Resources	Print	Both (Print & E-Resource)	Total No Response
1	IIITDM Jabalpur	6	1	3	10
2	NIRTH, Jabalpur	3	1	5	09
3	DWR Jabalpur	1	0	4	05
Total No Responses					24

Users' preference for print or E-Resource or both in centrally funded institutions of Jabalpur Madhya Pradesh.

Based on the data presented in Table 1, we have analyzed the preferences for different resource formats- E-resources, Print resources, and a combination of both- across three institutions, IIITDM, NIRTH, and DWR Jabalpur. At IIITDM, six respondents preferred E-resources, indicating a strong inclination toward digital material for accessing information. This suggests that most users at this institution find electronic formats more convenient and accessible, possibly due to ease of searching, portability, and immediate availability. Additionally, three respondents preferred a combination of print and E-resources, highlighting a segment of users who value the advantages of digital and physical materials for their study or research needs. Interestingly, only one response was recorded in favor of print resources alone, suggesting a minimal dependency on traditional printed material among the respondents from this institution. In the case of ICMR NIRTH, three respondents favored E-resources, while a higher number – five respondents preferred a combination of print and E-resources. This indicates that many users at this institution still rely on printed materials alongside digital resources, possibly due to the nature of their research.

Furthermore, one response was recorded in favor of Print resources, showing that while digital access is essential, there is still a minor preference for printed materials. At ICAR DWR, only one respondent indicated a preference for E-resources, showing relatively low adaptation of digital materials among the users surveyed. However, four respondents preferred combinations of both, suggesting that most users in this institution rely on digital and physical resources to meet their information needs. Notably, no response was recorded in favor of print resources alone, indicating that while printed materials are still in use, they are primarily supplemented by E-resources rather than being relied upon exclusively. These findings show a trend where E-resources are gaining popularity across institutions, but the number of users still prefer a hybrid approach

Table 2

Users' preference for Download the information or only read the information in centrally funded institutions of Jabalpur Madhya Pradesh				
S. No.	Name of Institutions	Download the information	Only read the information	Total No Response
1	IITDM Jabalpur	4	5	9
2	NIRTH Jabalpur	6	4	10
3	DWR Jabalpur	4	1	5
Total No of Responses				24

Based on the data presented in Table 2, we have analyzed user preferences regarding accessing e-resources across three institutions. At IITDM, out of the total responses recorded, four users preferred downloading the information while accessing e-resources. This indicates that these users find it more convenient to store the information for offline reference, possibly for further study or future use. On the other hand, five respondents preferred only reading the information online without downloading it. This suggests that they may find online reading sufficient for their needs, possibly due to easy access to the internet or limited storage space on their device. In the case of NIRTH, six respondents favoured downloading the information while using e-resources. This suggests that a higher number of users at this institution prefer to have access to the material even when offline.

Meanwhile, four users prefer reading the information without downloading it, highlighting a segment of users who engage with e-resources without needing local storage. At DWR, a total of four respondents showed a preference for downloading the information, whereas only one respondent preferred to read the information online without downloading it. This highlights a strong inclination among users at this institution towards downloading e-resources, possibly due to the nature of their research or study patterns.

Overall, the findings indicate that while a notable proportion of users in all three institutions prefer to read e-resources without downloading them, a more significant segment still leans towards downloading the information for future reference.

Conclusion:

The outcome of this study demonstrates a clear preference for e-resources among users in centrally funded institutions of Jabalpur, Madhya Pradesh, who have varying degrees of inclination towards print and hybrid formats. IITDM

Jabalpur shows strong preferences for e-resources, while NIRTH displays a more balanced approach between print and digital resources, with minimal inclination towards exclusive print use. The study also revealed that many users across all institutions prefer downloading e-resources for future reference rather than reading online. This trend underlines the growing reliance on digital content for academic and research activities.

Suggestions:

To make the most efficient use of e-resources, improve digital literacy initiatives among the users of libraries of central government-funded institutions of Jabalpur Madhya Pradesh. Keep upgrading internet infrastructure to make it easier to access online resources. Keep collections up to date for users who would instead use more conventional resources. Hold frequent feedback sessions to make sure resource offerings meet user needs. Libraries can also conduct orientation programs for library users to inform them about their collections and how to use them. These are a few suggestions for making efficient use of e-resources.

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